

Appendix B. Detailed Results of the Delphi Process

Table B1

Detailed Results of the Delphi Process

Code	Original guideline	Agreement categories	Wave 1		Wave 2		Wave 3		
			% Agree	Comments	Revised guideline	% Agree	Comments	Revised guideline	% Agree
General guidelines for the prevention of violent extremism									
G1	Build and maintain a relationship of trust (or a therapeutic alliance) with the individuals you help. Trust remains the key element.	Strongly disagree	0.0%	Adopted					
		Disagree	0.0%						
		Agree	6.6%						
		Strongly agree	93.4%						
G2	Consider using non-formal settings to reduce wariness.	Strongly disagree	3.3%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three people thought this recommendation was unclear. What is a non-formal setting and wariness? • This does not apply to counselling visits. • Need to see evidence in support of this statement before feeling comfortable endorsing it. • Two people noted that this recommendation did not apply to all settings. One suggested adding “If the setting allows, think about...” at the beginning of the sentence, and another suggested rephrasing it as follows: “If you are working in an institutional setting, think about XYZ to maximize your clients' comfort and minimize.” • Three people pointed out the need for safety in non-formal settings: The non-formal setting should be safe for both the practitioner and the client. • Two people suggested to contextualize the recommendation by adding: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This may depend on the POC, as some individuals may be 	0.0%	Adopted			
		Disagree	3.3%		• Ensure that meeting conditions maximize the sense of comfort of the individuals you help while taking into account the realities of your work (e.g., institutional vs informal setting) and the safety of both parties.		0.0%		
		Agree	26.2%				10.2%		
		Strongly agree	67.2%				89.9%		

Code	Original guideline	Agreement categories	Wave 1		Wave 2		Wave 3	
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				<p>highly educated and more comfortable in a professional setting, while others may be overwhelmed if it feels too professional.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider feasibility from a budgetary/safety perspective. Non-formal settings may be too all-encompassing and should be considered on a case-by-case basis, with perhaps a preference for non-formal settings if a set of conditions is met. Two people recommended clients' active involvement in deciding the setting. One participant suggested mentioning that while less formal, these environments need a clear ethical framework. Two individuals added the notion of having to adapt when choosing intervention sites. One did so by specifying that it is necessary to adapt to the context, while the other mentioned the need to adapt to the youth (some find a formal setting rewarding and appreciate it). Finally, one participant suggested replacing the term "clients" with "individuals." 				
G4	Develop the person's sense of agency and problem-solving skills by asking interactive questions and seeking an open dialogue.	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree	1.6% 0.0% 9.8% 88.5%	Adopted				
G5	Avoid being judgmental and/or letting conflict escalate when discussing	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree	0.0% 1.6% 9.8%	Adopted				

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	the extremist views of the individuals you help. Challenging people on their extremist views may result in these views becoming more crystalized. Take a flexible and respectful approach anchored in a relationship of trust.	Strongly agree	88.5%						
G6	Seek training and up-to-date information on issues related to violent radicalization. Do not hesitate to ask more experienced colleagues or teams if you feel overwhelmed by a situation (while maintaining confidentiality). Training topics include but are not limited to the following: cultural sensitivity, mental health and psychosocial issues, trauma-informed care, harm reduction, human rights, vulnerability/needs/ risk assessment, violent extremist groups and narratives, the role of the Internet/social media, effective prevention approaches, ideology and dogma, and misinformation.	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree	0.0% 1.6% 13.1% 85.2%	Adopted					
G7	The generalizability of PVE programs appears to be limited. Therefore, practitioners should refrain from transplanting a program “as is” from one context to another. Practitioners must adapt and tailor programs to local contexts.	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree	1.6% 3.3% 13.1% 82.0%	Adopted					
G8	The lack of prevention programs targeting far-left, far-right, anti-	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree	3.3% 8.2% 9.8%	• The lack of clarity in this statement was raised by participants,	There is a need for PVE programs addressing far-left,	0.0% 2.0% 22.4%	• Several people mentioned that the different forms of radicalization should be	Given the limited data on prevention programs addressing far-left, far-right,	3.5% 3.5% 36.8%

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	government, and/or single-issue violent radicalization and extremism stands in stark contrast with the prevalence of these phenomena in many regions around the globe. Such programs should be designed, implemented, and evaluated in areas where these forms of violent extremism exist.	Strongly agree	78.7%	<p>especially with respect to the “and/or single issue” part:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cautious about recommending a major rollout and scaling up for primary and secondary programs because evidence concerning their success is currently scant. • Very clear definitions of what comprises problematic forms of “far left,” “far right,” and so on ought to be developed before recommending a whole suite of new programs • This is a general statement inviting many different responses depending on the context/country. Change the first sentence to “prevention programs more often tend to target forms of extremism that are perceived as a problem by majorities and neglect other forms of extremism that may nonetheless be very prevalent.” • Change the first sentence to “stands in stark contrast to the prevalence of such forms of violent radicalization (sic), which appear in regions of the world considered less affected by violent radicalization with ideological or religious reference, but just as disturbing.” • I’m not sure that specific programs should be designed to 	far-right, and single-issue (e.g., misogyny) violent radicalization. Practitioners, researchers, and policymakers should encourage the implementation and evaluation of such programs, especially in regions where these forms of extremism are prevalent.	75.5%	<p>approached in a more global and transversal way:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a need to develop prevention programs that address violent radicalization in a cross-cutting manner, allowing for all forms of violent extremism to be tackled. • More comprehensive programs can help prevent and assess several types of radicalization and help avoid the damaging effects of programs focused on only one type of radicalization. • For example, “There is a need for PVE programs addressing far-left, far-right, and/or single-issue (e.g., misogyny) violent radicalization.” Combine rather than separate different types of radicalization because a person can be misogynistic and far-right, for example. • While we may not need programs addressing every issue, we should be able to work with all individuals, regardless of the source of their radicalization. • The recommendation could target “specific and combined forms of violent radicalization.” Naming just a few types may reveal a bias, so such wording should be avoided. • Link to human rights (e.g., anti-discrimination, anti-hate speech, freedom of expression, etc.)? • Encourage, research root causes, and implement and evaluate these programs. • Two people suggested changing/removing the section, “especially in regions where these forms of extremism are prevalent:” • “Present” might be a better word than “prevalent” as it suggests 	<p>and single-issue (e.g., misogyny) violent extremism, practitioners, researchers, and policymakers should encourage the implementation and evaluation of programs that specifically target these types of violent radicalization and/or combine different forms of extremism.</p> <p>Not adopted</p>	56.1%

Code	Original guideline	Agreement categories	Wave 1		Wave 2		Wave 3	
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				tackle only one type of ideology. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> It may be that there is a lack of programs specifically designed for PVE, but that does not mean that programs designed to strengthen protective factors do not exist. Change “from the far left” to “for the far left.” One person suggested completing the second sentence with “and in regions not familiar with these forms.” Another suggested ending the recommendation with “and taking into account the specificities of each region.” 			a more intensive problem. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The absence or presence of a prevention program is not related to the prevalence of radicalization in a particular region. One person mentioned that PVE programs were not always useful and that the evidence of their effectiveness was not compelling. It would be better to say that such programs were only one response to radicalization. 	
G9	A successful program may become harmful if handled without due sensitivity. Practitioners should, therefore, be adequately trained to deal with the complex issues that this type of work involves, including risk assessment, case management and follow-up, cultural sensitivity, and the supervision of group dynamics in group-based programs.	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree	0.0% 0.0% 16.4% 83.6%	Adopted (as this recommendation was closely related to recommendation G6, it was merged with the latter)				
G10	If funding enables it, evaluation models should be designed at the onset of programs to ensure methodologically robust evaluations. Stronger data concerning PVE programs are urgently needed.	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree	0.0% 1.6% 13.1% 85.2%	Adopted				
G11	When evaluating prevention programs, conflicts of interest and	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree	0.0% 3.3% 18.0%	Adopted				

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			% Agree	Comments	Revised guideline	% Agree	Comments	Revised guideline	% Agree	
	potential biases should be kept to a minimum or be explicitly disclosed if unavoidable.	Strongly agree	81.7%							
Guidelines for online prevention of violent extremism										
O1	Be interested in the online habits of your clients. Find out how, when, and for how long they use the Internet/social media. You could ask: a) which sites and forums they visit; b) how they react and respond to the content they consume; c) what content they share and how widely, and D) what needs are being fulfilled by the Internet/social media.	Strongly disagree	0.0%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Five people commented on the issue of trust, advising that practitioners be aware of the risk of losing trust when their inquiry becomes too intrusive. People's privacy and personal integrity should always be respected. Two people commented on the practical and legal challenges surrounding surveillance of online behavior, suggesting that exploring online/offline habits may amount to surveillance, which could threaten trust. Should such work not be (largely) left to intelligence agencies? Three people commented on engaging with online material, saying that practitioners should differentiate and identify active and passive seekers of online content. Emphasis should be put on why a client uses social media rather than on how or when they do. Similar online behaviors may not always mean the same thing. The duration of 	Be open to exploring the online habits of individuals you help while respecting privacy and avoiding being intrusive, as this may threaten trust. Similar online behaviors may not mean the same to different individuals. Therefore, the main concern should be whether social media relations (real or imagined) and other online behaviors are replacing real-life relations and negatively impacting the person.	0.0%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clarify the term "explore" to avoid confusion about its scope (it does not mean the same thing to everyone). It can be done in an adult context, but what about children, for whom parents already (often) control access to the Internet? One person suggested replacing "have a negative impact on the individual" with "contributing to the individual's radicalization to violence." It's not always necessary to check if virtual contacts replace real contacts, but rather if these virtual contacts and their behaviors are reproduced in reality and/or if they influence the individual. 	Be open to discussing the online habits of the people you help. Make sure you have permission if they are minors. Remember to respect their privacy and avoid being intrusive, as this could threaten the bond of trust that you need to establish and maintain. Be aware that online behaviors may not have the same impact on different people. Therefore, the central concern should be whether relationships developed through the Internet and social media (real or imagined), as well as other online behaviors, negatively influence real-life relationships and/or contribute to the radicalization of the individual.	5.3%	
		Disagree	3.3%			4.3%			5.3%	
		Agree	24.6%			17.0%		Not adopted	26.3%	

Code	Original guideline	Agreement categories	Wave 1		Wave 2		Wave 3		
			% Agree	Comments	Revised guideline	% Agree	Comments	Revised guideline	% Agree
		Strongly agree	72.1%	<p>Internet use may be irrelevant; the main concern should be whether social media relations (real or imagined) are replacing real-life relations.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two participants mentioned that the focus should not be on online habits. One suggested that it would be better to add “If discussions about social media use arise, are you interested in...” at the beginning of the sentence. • One person said that he/she was unsure how, when, and for how long a person was online reflected the way social media is used. • One person wondered who the leaders/peers of online influencers were. • One person recommended removing question “d,” as it could interfere with the therapeutic relationship and require the ability to step back and reflect on one's behavior. • One person suggested that the term “client” should not be used. 		78.7%			63.2%

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O2	Avoid asking your clients only about their consumption of violent/hateful material, as doing so may give them the impression of being investigated. Ask questions about offline and non-radicalized aspects of their lives as well.	Strongly disagree	6.6%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Three people recommended using a contextual approach—depending on your role as a practitioner (e.g., if you are associated with the police, the people you help might have a reason to suspect you). Also, whether or not to use this approach depends on the client: If violent/hateful materials are of significant interest to them and play an important role in building their worldviews, you should discuss them. In the case of a lawyer-client relationship, constructive dialogue about the relevance of such consumption would be important. Two people recommended a temporal sequence for asking questions, i.e., asking about the client's life and identity before discussing ideology. It is important to ask about all aspects of their lives, including online and offline interests, at the appropriate time. It is all about when and how you ask questions. Three people compared this recommendation with recommendations O1 and G5: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> One person stated that questions about the consumption of violent/ hateful material should be asked with 	If you notice that the individuals you help are actively consuming and/or propagating hateful and violent extremist content online (e.g., they regularly participate in discussion forums of extremist groups or search and share violent/hateful content on social media), you should take time to discuss how this content connects to offline behaviors and other aspects of their lives.	0.0%	Adopted	
		Disagree	11.5%			0.0%		
		Agree	9.8%			2.1%		

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		Strongly agree	72.1%	<p>recommendations O1 and G5 in mind, i.e., developing an interest in the overall online habits of the client and doing so respectfully while refraining from making value judgments.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One person asserted that this recommendation contradicted recommendation O1. • One person suggested attaching this recommendation to O1. • One person argued that clients were intelligent enough to know when they were in these processes and that they would pick up on this. It is, therefore, essential to build trust first. • One participant suggested that it should be “hateful, violent or extremist material online.” • One participant suggested that what is considered hateful or violent material should be clarified (and suggested that it could be something like “complete forms of propaganda that incite hatred or violence”). The same person also suggested rewording the recommendation proposal as it implies that the client is being duped, and this could affect the trust relationship. • One participant advised the wording “don’t explore consumption first...” at the beginning of the sentence to stress that the online experience is not the only sphere of interest. 		97.9%			
O3	Pay particular attention if	Strongly disagree	1.6%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two people pointed out 	Pay particular	0.0%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One participant mentioned 	Be particularly careful if you	3.5%

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	you notice that your clients are actively consuming and/or propagating violent extremist content online (e.g., regularly participate in radical forums, search and share violent or hateful content on social media, and express violent intentions or threats). If they do, before taking immediate action, consult a local multidisciplinary team specialized in violent radicalization and risk assessment of violent behavior (https://cpnprev.ca/themap).	Disagree Agree Strongly agree	8.2% 14.8% 75.4%	that a local multidisciplinary team specialized in violent radicalization and risk assessment of violent behavior may not be available, especially in smaller settings. • Two people found this recommendation too long and convoluted: • The first person said that this recommendation contained two distinct parts and that he/she agreed with the first part but not the second. • The second person identified this recommendation as a “fruit salad” (too much is thrown into it and should be split up because of differences in behavior). He/she recommended separating participation in forums/consuming violent multimedia from making threats/expressing violent intent. • Three people expressed the need for clarification: • What does “immediate action” mean? • Clarify that radical forums are not illegal, but inciting violence or sharing content that incites violence is. • Add “threat assessment” to the wording, as “risk assessment” may be insufficient. • Two people pointed out the need to include offline behaviors as well. • One participant suggested that the terms “conspiratorial” and “extremist” be preferred to “hateful”	attention if you notice that individuals you help express violent intentions or threats online (or offline). Before taking any immediate drastic measure (e.g., reporting them to law enforcement agencies), assess the level of risk/threat and consult the appropriate resources if you are not equipped to do so. 1) Remember to always work within the legal framework of your country/ profession and honor your professional code of ethics. 2) Remember that misreporting a person to law enforcement may jeopardize your trust relationship and increase the individual’s sense of grievance, injustice, and ostracization.	0.0% 23.4% 76.6%	that the additions following the recommendation were redundant and could create a reluctance to report problematic behavior. • Several suggested removing or changing “to law enforcement” to “third party actors” to include all possible stakeholders that could be alerted, as any reporting may lead to loss of trust. • The wording “strong actions” could be replaced with “decisive actions,” “high consequence actions,” or “aimed at activating a control.” One person mentioned that “drastic/energetic” was not appropriate, as a referral is not necessarily drastic or harmful, and clinicians can collaborate/coexist with security in advancing violence prevention. • One person preferred to use “do, unless” to “do not, unless” to advocate reporting violent/threatening behavior, etc., to authorities. Instead of mentioning not alerting authorities too quickly, the person suggested reporting the behavior unless there was a good reason not to. • Expand “shows violent intent or makes threats” and add “to self or others.”	notice that the person you are helping is expressing violent intentions or making threats online or offline. Before taking any serious action (e.g., reporting them to law enforcement agencies), assess the level of risk/threat and consult the appropriate resources. 1) Remember to always work within the legal framework of your country/ profession and honor your professional code of ethics. 2) Remember that misreporting a person may jeopardize your trust relationship and increase the individual’s sense of injustice and ostracization. Not adopted	3.5% 29.8% 63.2%		

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				<p>and “violent” because they are less limiting and more representative of the content consumed online by most radicalized individuals.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This recommendation a) should be related to laws of professional confidentiality (in many countries, that type of action would be illegal) and b) relies on the local team’s knowledge and capacity. How can we be certain that a team has better tools than a professional to handle the issue? Wider drivers for radicalization should be considered, especially as information is now often shared on encrypted platforms. The wording “forums spreading violent extremist rhetoric” was suggested instead of “radical forums” by one individual, who also suggested replacing “draconian actions” with “calling for enforcement (reporting, security measures, etc.)” Finally, one individual stated that he did not understand the purpose of the hyperlink. 				
O4	Pay attention to the overlap between online and offline behaviors, as they are intrinsically linked in our modern world.	<p>Strongly disagree</p> <p>Disagree</p> <p>Agree</p> <p>Strongly agree</p>	<p>4.9%</p> <p>1.6%</p> <p>19.7%</p> <p>73.8%</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two people voiced their concerns about the wording of the recommendation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unsure about the word “intrinsically.” What does “paying attention” mean? Three people explained that while the recommendation was valuable, it was important to recognize that online and offline behaviors may not always be intrinsically linked. One person suggested changing the first 	As this recommendation was closely related to recommendations O1 and O2 (see above), it was merged with them before the start of the second wave			

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			% Agree	Comments	Revised guideline	% Agree	Comments	Revised guideline
				<p>sentence to "pay attention to how your client's online and offline lives interplay, especially if the person is experiencing distress or conflict."</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two participants warned that some people use the Internet as a platform to express a different personality (e.g., avatars) that is not and/or will never be them. Very often, individuals have two personas and focusing on the links between them can lead one down a dark alley. In order to account for the possibility of a divide and the construction of two online/offline identities, one participant suggested replacing this first sentence with "try to understand the interactions between online and offline life." One person stated that the rise in autism spectrum as a vulnerability factor needed to be considered. Online sites provide an emotionally simple forum for affected individuals to interact with others. One person considered the recommendation to be true if the online behavior was nonviolent One person felt this recommendation was too general. 				

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O5	Help develop the critical thinking and digital literacy of your clients by referring them to resources such as a) SERENE-RISK (https://www.serene-risc.ca/en/); b) Microsoft Digital Literacy course (https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/digitalliteracy/home).	Strongly disagree	4.9%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two people feared this recommendation would come across as condescending. Three people said they could not comment on this recommendation without learning more about the recommended resources. One person explained that they agreed in principle but needed to know more. One person said they were indifferent about the “digital literacy” part of the recommendation. Three people advised that before referring clients to resources, practitioners should make sure clients were able to understand the content of these resources. One person suggested adding more moderated sites and references, and another suggested that less technical resources be used as well (i.e., common sense and values such as respect, DH, etc.). One participant questioned giving examples of resources (especially the Microsoft course so as not to advertise them), as the resources should be produced in the person's cultural context and with stakeholders they trust. Two people argued that the recommended resources were not appropriate for developing critical thinking, authenticating online information, or recognizing and deconstructing online hate. Conversely, two participants suggested other relevant resources: MediaSmart (http://mediasmarts.ca), 	If useful or needed, contribute to the digital literacy and critical thinking of the individuals you help. This will help them authenticate valid information online, which may, in turn, help them recognize and deconstruct violent extremist messages.	2.1%	Adopted	
		Disagree	1.6%			2.1%		
		Agree	19.7%			6.4%		
		Strongly agree	73.8%			89.4%		

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				<p>ABC Life Literacy (https://abclifeliteracy.ca), and Safe on Web (https://safeonweb.be).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One person outright called this recommendation “stupid” and doubted clients would take this course. • One person recommended translating the resources. Recommended resources are only available in English and, therefore, not accessible to people who do not speak it. • Three people agreed that there was a need to develop critical thinking. One person specifically highlighted the need for young people to be able to decode extremist messaging when it is wrapped in humor (e.g., memes) or everyday-like situations (e.g., YouTube videos). • Another person mentioned that dialogue and trust must be established before developing critical thinking skills and that this must be in response to a person’s questioning for it to work. • One person believed clients had already developed critical thinking and digital literacy and that the problem was more about social, political, and economic injustices. • One person suggested replacing the beginning of the sentence with “help your clients develop their digital literacy by exercising critical thinking Skills regarding the content they access.” • One person considered 				

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				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the recommendation to be helpful for tertiary prevention programs. One person also suggested that this recommendation should be separated into two, as the development of critical thinking skills (cognitive reflexivity) and digital literacy were different vulnerability factors. 				
Guidelines for primary and secondary prevention of violent extremism								
P1	Researchers and practitioners may benefit from reframing primary	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree	3.3% 4.9% 19.7%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Three people found the recommendation unclear: 	Programs should not be expected to prevent an attack from	0.0% 0.0% 17.0%	Adopted	

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	and secondary prevention programs from a public health perspective. Clearly, such programs are not designed to prevent an attack from occurring but rather to reduce the risk—over the medium to long term—that an individual may embark on a path toward violent radicalization.	Strongly agree	72.1%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The recommendation has two separate ideas, and this does not make sense. What is the original frame that is incorrect? And what is the better frame? Are you saying that primary and secondary PVE programs are framed as being designed to prevent attacks? The language of the recommendation is confusing. Using a PH perspective may be better than what? “Clearly“ should not be in a recommendation. “Such programs:” what programs? “Over the medium to long term” is unclear. The parallel with public health was criticized by three people: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> One participant suggested deleting the first sentence, as he did not believe there was necessarily a link to public health. One participant said that, although the parallel was exciting, the epidemiological model did not apply effectively to radicalization. The third one disagreed with the suggestion to apply a public health perspective for political reasons. This expert also suggested replacing “benefit for...” with “gain for...” Two people recommended adopting a larger focus at the group and societal level. 	occurring but rather to reduce the risk—over the medium to long term—that an individual may embark on a path toward violent radicalization. Well-designed primary and secondary PVE programs that target relevant risk and protective factors have generally been found to be effective and should be encouraged.	83.0%		

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				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The key focus should be on a general perspective of “care” and “safeguarding” rather than “security.” Consider an alternative phrasing that does not assume a certain linear direction, such as “that an individual could be at risk of engaging with...” Programs delivered in prisons or deradicalization detention centers should be the exceptions, as it is impossible to avoid the need for a security “lens” in these cases. Another participant suggested adding “and social cohesion” after “public health.” One participant suggested replacing the second sentence with, “In fact, these programs are not designed to prevent an attack from occurring but to increase/consolidate collective resilience factors and decrease vulnerability factors that are associated with attitudes that legitimize violence.” 				
P2	Primary and secondary prevention programs should not arbitrarily	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree	0.0% 3.3% 16.4%	Adopted				

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	target any specific gender, cultural, religious, or ethnic group. This does not mean that programs should not be tailored for a specific audience. Rather, programs should avoid stigmatizing groups by assuming that membership in any of the above groups constitutes a risk factor for involvement in violent extremism. Programs must, however, be age-Appropriate.	Strongly agree	80.3%					
P3	Prevention programs based on surveillance or intelligence gathering	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree	1.6% 16.4% 21.3%	• Most of the people agreed with the recommendation but	Trust relationships with individuals and collaborations with	0.0% 2.1% 8.5%	Adopted	

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	(e.g., censorship programs in universities or hotlines to report “suspicious activity”) should be avoided, as they appear counterproductive (i.e., they cause more harm than benefits).	Strongly agree	60.7%	<p>continued to argue in favor of surveillance or intelligence gathering in certain contexts and for different purposes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While surveillance and hotlines should not be the main prevention effort, police benefit from them in countering crimes. • General-population involvement in the early detection of potential extremists is important if prevention programs stay short of panopticon-style surveillance. • Surveillance and intel gathering are important for disruption, but there should be a balance between surveillance/intel gathering and community engagement. • Some intelligence gathering could avoid potential or imminent threats posed by violent extremists. • What information is gathered and to whom it gets directed depends on the program’s design. • This recommendation is unclear. There is a big difference between encouraging reporting of suspicious activity in the public domain among strangers and encouraging such behavior among intimates (e.g., Grossman and Thomas). Among intimates, there seem to be ways of reporting concerns of violent 	<p>communities are likely to be harmed if programs designed for primary or secondary prevention conflate surveillance/ information gathering with psychosocial/ mental health support. If your program contains components that may be used for surveillance/ information gathering, be transparent with individuals and clearly explain the limits of your confidentiality commitments, as dictated by your professional code of conduct.</p>	87.0%		

Code	Original guideline	Agreement categories	Wave 1		Wave 2		Wave 3	
			% Agree	Comments	Revised guideline	% Agree	Comments	Revised guideline
				<p>radicalization to authorities that are not necessarily counterproductive.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Surveillance and hotlines themselves are not counterproductive. It is the way a program is communicated to the public (i.e., the awareness campaign) that is often problematic. Frequently, it fails to address emergent stigmas that cause such programs to be counterproductive. Four participants disagreed with the guideline <ul style="list-style-type: none"> One said it was difficult to be specific about the topic. Another said that it may have been too radical, specifying instead that these programs should never be used alone. The hotline example was problematic and should be removed. The caution against using PVE programs for surveillance and intelligence gathering should be stronger. Two people mentioned that there needed to be more clarity on the objectives/target audiences: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> One said that there should be more transparency about who was using these tools and a better distinction between the responsibilities of those who were asked to use such tools (they should not at the same time be asked to act in other ways). The other added the clarification that 				

Code	Original guideline	Agreement categories	Wave 1		Wave 2		Wave 3	
			% Agree	Comments	Revised guideline	% Agree	Comments	Revised guideline
				<p>programs should declare whether they were a listening or an alerting service.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support online reporting tools that are focused on “social responsibility” for keeping us all safe. This means it is not a “report a poacher” initiative but a general safety tip for all forms of violence or concerning behavior. Refer to PSST World and the BC Government ERASE Initiative: news.gov.bc.ca “Student Safety Increased Through School-Police Partnership” November 21, 2019. Finally, one expert suggested replacing the end of the sentence with “should be reviewed and reinforced with follow-up awareness to better understand and support them if needed.” 				
Guidelines suggested by participants not specifically derived from systematic reviews								
NR1		Strongly disagree Disagree Agree			Conduct a comprehensive mental health and	0.0% 2.1% 10.6%	Adopted	

Code	Original guideline	Agreement categories	Wave 1		Wave 2		Wave 3	
			% Agree	Comments	Revised guideline	% Agree	Comments	Revised guideline
		Strongly agree			psychosocial evaluation in order to address mental health issues such as trauma and their relation to practical needs or stressors. If this is not possible in your context, make sure that you have access to specialized support in this area.	87.2%		
NR2		Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree			Pay attention to the larger social ecology of individuals who are involved in violent extremism. Consider families, friends, and institutions in order to identify potential risk and protective factors and, if possible, involve them in the intervention.	4.3% 0.0% 14.9% 80.9%	Adopted	
NR3		Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree			Pay attention to the cultural environment of individuals involved in violent extremism, especially the roles of racism and systemic discrimination as catalysts toward anger and feelings Of exclusion.	4.3% 4.3% 10.6% 80.9%	Adopted	
NR4		Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree			As far as possible, work with a multidisciplinary team within your organization.	0.0% 2.1% 12.8% 85.0%	Adopted	
NR5		Strongly disagree Disagree Agree			Include a gender-based approach in your evaluation and	0.0% 4.3% 10.6%	Adopted	

Code	Original guideline	Agreement categories	Wave 1		Wave 2		Wave 3		
			% Agree	Comments	Revised guideline	% Agree	Comments	Revised guideline	% Agree
		Strongly agree			intervention plans to respond to the different gendered drivers involved in violent extremism.	85.1%			
NR6		Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree			Before meeting with individuals involved in violent extremism, make sure your institution has a safety plan and guidelines regarding escalation to law enforcement.	2.1% 2.1% 8.5% 87.2%	Adopted		
NR7		Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree			Understand, evaluate, and respond to the needs of the individuals you help (e.g., being marginalized, not having a job) that are given a voice through violent extremist narratives/groups.	4.3% 8.5% 31.9% 55.3%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Several people disagreed with the wording "respond to the needs of the individuals you help." They advocated for "support the needs" instead. Replace with "support these people to solve their needs/problems." It is impossible to solve the socio-economic problems of all individuals. Avoid making unrealistic commitments. If you do so, the responsibility becomes too great for the provider. "Have clear communication with your counterpart about what can and cannot be expected." Some needs cannot be solved by intervention alone 	Try to understand, assess, and help the persons find answers to their needs (e.g., reducing marginalization, accessing employment, etc.) So that they do not seek those answers from violent extremist narratives/groups.	1.8% 1.8% 19.3% 77.2%

